

Stacked Ensemble Predictions of (n,2n) Cross-sections

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear data, particularly reaction cross-sections, are essential for the simulation of nuclear systems. Experimental datasets are frequently incomplete or inconsistent, especially for exotic nuclides which have little to no empirical data, leaving theoretical libraries such as TENDL and JENDL5 as the only sources of exotic nuclide predictions. Therefore, there is scope to explore the use of machine learning (ML) as an alternative source of cross-section predictions. This study investigated the prediction of (n,2n) cross-sections for medium-mass nuclides ($20 \leq A \leq 200$) using ENDF/B-VIII data for training and benchmarking. A stacked ensemble incorporating XGBoost, random forest, and neural network base models with a ridge regression meta-model was evaluated against the individual performance of the aforementioned base models, using aggregated mean squared error (MSE) and win rate metrics. A stacked ensemble achieved superior aggregated performance to all baseline learners, with an average MSE of 1.84310^{-2} and a win rate of 37%, outperforming all base models. These findings suggest that stacked ensembles, with sophisticated meta model design, can deliver superior (n,2n) cross-section predictions compared to individual learners.

Keywords: Nuclear, Data, Cross-sections, Machine Learning, Ensembling

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate nuclear data is essential for the safe modelling of systems in energy production, medicine, and national security. Experimental measurements, such as cross-sections, are compiled in databases like EXFOR, but coverage remains incomplete. Consequently, theoretical codes such as TALYS [1] and Empire [2] are used to supplement experimental data, producing theoretical libraries which cannot be easily validated. This is especially pronounced for exotic nuclides which possess little to no empirical data, leaving theoretical libraries such as TENDL and JENDL5 as the only source of exotic nuclide data. However, relying on reaction theory alone creates a single point of failure, motivating the use of machine learning (ML). Recent works have demonstrated the potential for ML methods to act as an alternative source of data. Significant recent works include the use of structured statistical learning models [3], as well as neural network based approaches including graph neural networks [4], Bayesian neural networks [5], and Dense neural networks [6]. While these methods represent recent important advances, their models have not been used within this work. Of direct relevance are comparable studies that have applied simpler neural network architectures and XGBoost with feature importance analysis to improve prediction precision [7]. However, limitations remain: neural network-based methods exhibit large errors near critical thresholds [8], and XGBoost produces unacceptable deviations in 11.5% of medium-mass cases [7]. This project builds on the prior research by similarly targeting the (n,2n) reaction for medium-mass nuclides ($20 \leq A \leq 200$) [8, 9], with the objective of investigating more sophisticated ML architectures as a means of achieving superior predictive accuracy to the models used within the aforementioned works. Stacked ensembling, a method in which multiple different models' predictions are combined by a final meta-model, is the architecture on which this project will focus.

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Stacking was pursued due to its proven ability to leverage complementary strengths of different ML models. Prior studies in materials modelling and environmental prediction demonstrated significant improvements when using stacking over single models [10, 11, 12]. Here, stacking was hypothesised to address contextual weaknesses- situations in which individual models perform poorly under certain conditions, patterns, or feature magnitudes. By stacking, models can compensate for each other’s blind spots, improving aggregated performance.

The scope of the project is restricted to $(n,2n)$ reactions within the specified mass region, as prior research indicates that ML predictions are most reliable within this range. Only previously established baseline models are replicated for comparison, and predictions are validated exclusively against datasets derived from ENDF/B-VIII.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Data

The dataset compiled include the ENDF/B-VIII $(n,2n)$ reaction cross sections for the isotopes $20 \leq A \leq 200$ range, as well as 60 additional features describing the nuclear properties of each isotope where available. A full list of the features can be found in references [7, 13]. Additionally, an engineered feature was inserted: the normalized energy fraction, a ratio of the energy at a specific point in the cross-sectional spectrum to the maximum energy of that spectrum, was introduced to contextualize neutron energy by isotope. To enforce threshold energy learning, artificial zero cross-section entries were inserted at 0.3 MeV intervals up to the reaction threshold energies. Due to limitations in neural networks, which cannot handle missing values, incomplete entries had to be removed from the dataset, reducing the number of isotopes used considerably. The data was split into training and test sets, with full isotopes held out to prevent data leakage— that is, to ensure the model never sees, and therefore learns, any information from the isotopes it is later evaluated on.

2.2. Baseline Models

Three machine learning models were used as baseline models, due to their strong performance in predicting nuclear cross-sections in previous works. These were a neural network (TensorFlow Keras) [14], gradient-boosted regression tree (XGBoost) [15] and random forest model (Scikit-learn) [16]. The hyperparameters were optimised using Bayesian searches (Hyperopt), with the final set of hyperparameters displayed in Tables I, II, & III. Performance per isotope was measured using mean squared error (MSE), in the units of barns squared (b^2). Model performance across isotopes was evaluated using two aggregated metrics, the average MSE and the win rate, defined as the proportion of isotopes for which a model achieved the lowest MSE.

Table I. XGBoost hyperparameters

Hyperparameters	Value
Number of Trees	900
Max depth	8
Learning rate	0.0297
Subsampling	0.8
Feature Sampling	0.824
Leaf regularisation	1.2632
Maximum split threshold	0.027

Table II. Neural network hyperparameters

Symbol	Value
Number of layers	3
Nodes per layer	416
Activation Function	ReLU
Dropout rate	0.04829
Learning rate	9.0556×10^{-4}
Weight regularisation	0.008373
Batch size	64
Epochs	40

Table III. Random forest tree hyperparameters

Symbol	Value
Number of Trees	1200
Max Depth	50
Subsampling	0.63

2.3. Stacking

Stacking combines multiple base models whose predictions form inputs to a meta-model. In this study, predictions from the XGBoost, neural network, and random forest were passed to a ridge regression meta-model, which applied contextual weights based on proton number, charge, and energy. Variations of the ridge regression design were tested using different weighting strategies, and an iterative development process for the meta-model was used to converge on the final Ridge6 model, which produced the most promising results.

To make the meta-model robust to the stochastic nature of the base models, each base model $b \in \{\text{nn, xgb, rf}\}$ is executed R times, producing a vector of predictions $[\hat{y}_{i,b,1}, \dots, \hat{y}_{i,b,R}]$ for each row i . The mean prediction $\hat{y}_{i,b}$ is then calculated as follows:

$$\hat{y}_{i,b} = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \hat{y}_{i,b,r} \quad (1)$$

This mean value is passed to the meta model as the final output of each base model. A dynamic weight, $w_b(f, E, Z, A)$, dependent on the corresponding feature values, is applied to each base models final output. These are then combined to produced the stacked models prediction as follows:

$$\hat{y}_{i,S} = \hat{y}_{i,\text{nn}} w_{\text{nn}}(f, E, Z, A) + \hat{y}_{i,\text{xgb}} w_{\text{xgb}}(f, E, Z, A) + \hat{y}_{i,\text{rf}} w_{\text{rf}}(f, E, Z, A) \quad (2)$$

Where Z and A are the atomic and mass numbers, E is the absolute incident neutron energy, and f is the engineered normalised energy fraction. Additionally the total weight, $w_b(f, E, Z, A)$ of a base model b can be defined as:

$$w_b(f, E, Z, A) = w_{b,0} + f w_{b,f} + E w_{b,E} + Z w_{b,Z} + A w_{b,A} \quad (3)$$

Further to its use in Eq.1, the vector of predictions each base model produces, $[\hat{y}_{i,b,1}, \dots, \hat{y}_{i,b,R}]$, is used to calculate the variance of each base model, $v_{i,b}$ through the process of Eq.4.

$$v_{i,b} = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R (\hat{y}_{i,b,r} - \hat{y}_{i,b})^2 \quad (4)$$

The total row variance is aggregated across base learners, and defines a trust weight through the process of Eq. 5. This trust weight, x_i , is then incorporated into the ridge regressions models loss function, $J(w)$, in the left term of Eq. 6, down-weighting noisy rows and emphasising stable ones.

$$x_i = \frac{1}{1 + v_i}, \quad \text{where} \quad v_i = v_{i,1} + \dots + v_{i,b}, \quad \text{and} \quad 0 < x_i \leq 1, \quad (5)$$

$$J(w) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i (y_i - \hat{y}_{i,\text{St}})^2 + \alpha \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^2, \quad (6)$$

In Eq. 6: m is the number of isotopes tested over, n is the number of terms in Eq. 2, w_j is the weight for a given term of Eq. 2, and α is the weight regularisation term.

This means in practice that a large bias on a low variance row has a high trust weight, and therefore affects the coefficients more and the model adjusts itself noticeably. A large bias on a high variance row has a low trust weight, so it has little effect on the coefficients and the model mostly ignores the noisy signal.

2.4. Training

We use K-fold training to let both base and meta model train on all available data without leaking results to the model. The data is split into five folds. In each round base models train on four folds and predict the fifth fold. After each round models are reset and trained again with a new group of folds. Once all rounds are done every fold has predictions from each base model, forming the meta model's training data. Then the base models are retrained on all data and used to predict the test set, whose outputs the meta model combines into the final predictions. This allows all models to learn from the full dataset without data leakage. This is the premise of K-fold training. This project used a variation called Group-K-fold data, in which isotopes data is grouped, such that an individual isotopes data is not split across different folds.

3. RESULTS

Figure 1. Stacked Ensemble and Base Model Performance for the Ridge6 meta model

Table IV. Ridge6

Model	Avg MSE (b^2)	Win rate (%)
Neural Network	2.790e-01	24.7
XGBoost	2.239e-02	23.5
Random Forest	2.546e-02	14.8
Stacked Ensemble	1.843e-02	37.0

The Ridge6 ensemble achieved an average MSE of 1.84×10^{-2} , comfortably surpassing all three baseline models. Its win rate of 37% was also substantially higher than any individual learner. Performance patterns differed by mass region. Ridge6 achieved its strongest gains for lighter nuclides ($A \leq 96$), where its win rate was 43%, compared with 33% in heavier nuclides ($A \geq 134$). This contrasted with earlier ridge variants, which favoured heavier mass regions, suggesting that variance-weighted training allowed Ridge6 to capture under-represented light nuclide behaviour more effectively than previous iterations. Figure 1 illustrates the variation in performance of both the stacked ensemble and the individual base models across all isotopes. It is evident that the stacked ensemble's performance varies by isotope and, in some cases falls below that of its base models. The figure also offers valuable insight into the behaviour of the base learners, with the neural network demonstrating strong performance on average but for several large outliers such as Ar-41, Ba-139, Eu-152, & Os-188. This is consistent with its weaker aggregate metrics reported in Table IV. In contrast, both the random forest and XGBoost models exhibit more moderate yet consistent performances across isotopes.

Figure 2. Comparison of cross-section predictions for Kr-83

Figure 2 illustrates a case demonstrating the strong performance of the stacked ensemble. The meta model exhibits contextual awareness, relying on the more accurate Random Forest and XGBoost predictions near the threshold energy, and gradually shifting toward the neural network predictions as the spectrum approaches its peak between 13–20 MeV. However, the meta model's performance worsens toward the tail end of the spectrum, where its weighting becomes divided among the base models and it places excessive trust in the neural network predictions.

Figure 3. Comparison of cross-section predictions for K-40

Figure 3 presents a case in which the meta-model performs ideally, consistently selecting the most accurate base model predictions across the spectrum. However, its performance remains constrained by the inherent limitations of the base models themselves, illustrating a key limitation of stacked ensemble method, as their ability to improve results is ultimately bounded by the quality of the internal base models.

Figure 4. Comparison of cross-section predictions for Ge-74

Figure 4 illustrates a less common case in which the meta model's algorithm leads to poor selection of base model predictions. As a result, the stacked ensemble produces poor outputs both preceding the threshold energy, manifesting as a premature threshold prediction, and in overshooting the spectrum's maximum. Although the overall performance metrics presented in Table IV appear promising, they

conceal occasional cases where the stacked ensemble underperforms relative to its constituent base models. This variability of performance by isotope is a further limitation to the stacked ensemble.

Overall, the results demonstrated that a carefully constructed stacked ensemble can combine the contextual strengths of diverse base learners while mitigating individual weaknesses to provide more accurate results in aggregate. Overall the use of stacking as an ensembling technique can produce superior cross-section predictions for the $(n,2n)$ reaction than individual learners.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the use of stacked ensembles for predicting $(n,2n)$ cross-sections of medium-mass nuclides, using a stacked ensemble with an adapted ridge regression meta-model that combined XGBoost, random forest, and neural network base learners. The stacked ensemble achieved an average MSE of 1.84×10^{-2} and a win rate of 37%, outperforming all individual baseline models in both aggregated metrics. These results suggest that ensembling can deliver measurable improvements over individual learner approaches by leveraging their respective strengths.

The addition of a variance-weighted training scheme proved particularly effective, compared to previous iterations of meta models without it. This led to superior performance not only in aggregate metrics but also across under represented regions of the dataset, particularly the lower mass nuclides, which had made up less of the training data and as such had experienced weaker results by both the base and stacked models using previous iterations of the meta model.

The implications of these findings are that the use of stacked ensembling can produce more accurate $(n,2n)$ reaction cross-section predictions when a sophisticated approach is taken to the design of the meta-model. While further validation across additional reactions and libraries is required, the improvement in predictions increases the potential of ML architectures to provide data for nuclear applications over traditional reaction libraries.

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All features used in training:

Cross-section (barns), Atomic number, Mass number, Incident neutron energy, Neutron number, Mass excess (MeV), Nucleus binding energy (MeV), Binding energy (MeV/ nucleon), Atomic mass (u), One-neutron separation energy (MeV), Two-neutron separation energy (MeV), One-proton separation energy (MeV), Two-proton separation energy (MeV), Root-mean-square nuclear radius (fm), Pairing-energy term (MeV), Shell-correction energy (MeV), Ground-state total angular momentum (\hbar), Nuclear parity, Deformation parameter, Decay constant λ (s^{-1}), Boolean flag if Z is even (1 for even, 0 for odd), Boolean flag for A, Boolean flag for N, Quadrupole deformation parameter β_2 , Triaxiality angle γ (degrees), Octupole deformation parameter β_3 , Matter root-mean-square radius (fm), Neutron root-mean-square radius (fm), Proton root-mean-square radius (fm), Neutron shell gap energy (MeV), Proton shell gap energy (MeV), Neutron chemical potential (MeV), Proton chemical potential (MeV), Neutron separation energy for compound nucleus (MeV), Two-neutron separation energy for compound nucleus (MeV), Proton separation energy of the compound nucleus (MeV), Two-proton separation energy for

compound nucleus (MeV), Root-mean-square radius of the compound nucleus (fm), Mass excess of the compound nucleus (MeV), Total binding energy for compound nucleus (MeV), Binding energy per nucleon for compound nucleus (MeV per nucleon), Pairing-energy term for compound nucleus, Shell-correction energy of the compound nucleus, Ground-state total angular momentum of the compound nucleus, Parity of the compound nucleus, Deformation parameter of the compound nucleus, Decay-related term of the compound nucleus, Pairing-energy term of the daughter nucleus, Shell-correction energy of the daughter nucleus, Ground-state total angular momentum of the daughter nucleus, Parity of the daughter nucleus, Deformation parameter of the daughter nucleus, Decay-related term of the daughter nucleus, Neutron separation energy of the daughter nucleus (MeV), Two-neutron separation energy of the daughter nucleus (MeV), Proton separation energy of the daughter nucleus (MeV), Two-proton separation energy of the daughter nucleus (MeV), Root-mean-square radius of the daughter nucleus (fm), Mass excess of the daughter nucleus (MeV), Total binding energy of the daughter nucleus (MeV), Binding energy per nucleon of the daughter nucleus (MeV/nucleon).